

Role model and Parenting - The Building Blocks for A Juvenile to Be Delinquent or Nondelinquent: A Psychoanalytical Study in The Select Poems

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Abstract

“What Children see, Children do”, role modeling is a momentous progression in a child’s life. All children have a role model at some point in their lives. The point is who they see as their model. This may seem trivial whereas it creates an enormous impression on the impending behaviour and resolutions of the child. It is important for a child to have a social life. Peer and community may also affect the antisocial behaviour of a child. If a child is antisocial or excluded by the peer group, this may lead to stress, apprehension and downheartedness and may even shoddier psychological disturbances. This escalates the risk of crime among juveniles. Individuals tend to commit crime in their early ages. There is lack of awareness about how we can decrease crime tendency. Because people do not know the causes that push children into crime. There are various reasons for delinquency it can be psychological, economic, political and social. Where social problems are concerned, parental issues, family environment, peer and community, antisocial behaviour or exclusion, role modeling may be considered. This paper tries to answer the questions, whether Juvenile Delinquency is a social issue and how can it be recognised in the teaching or learning environment and what are the implications of Juvenile Delinquency for teachers and students? It analyses role modeling and parenting in the selected poems in the anthology titled *Teen Poems from behind Bars* poems written by youth at Denney Justice Center in Everett, Washington.

Keywords: Juvenile Delinquency, role model, antisocial behaviour, teaching and learning environment,

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Family milieu plays an important role in the nurturing process of a child. There are many juvenile crime rates all over the world, the hub for all these crimes starts from poor family milieu. Parents and members in the house often consider the changes and domestic violence in the family has nothing to do with the psychological disturbances of a child. Children are innocent beings they can easily be influenced. They imitate what they see and hear around them. Most of the children tend to be influenced by family members especially parents. Other few may be influenced by the people in the neighbourhood, teachers, peers, media icons and celebrities. Role models may vary according to the tastes and level of expectation of a child. It is substantial for the child to take right choices. In the anthology *Teen Poems from Behind bars*, there is a poem titled "Role Model" in which the teen boy says:

I've lived my life as a gangster
 But now it's time for me to say good-bye.
 I don't need this stuff in my life
 I'm going to be a Dad.
 I don't want this stuff for my son's life. (Lines 1-5)

The teen age boy is locked up behind the bars for being a gangster. He had always been influenced by wrong role model which later turned him into a gangster. He does not want his children to be influenced by the wrong role model like him. So, the boy seeks necessary ways to purify himself with good deeds so that the child can follow his good ways.

According to *Psychology Dictionary* (2000) "Juvenile Delinquency" is illegal behaviour by a minor that would be considered criminal against the state (vandalism, petty theft, auto theft, arson, rape etc.) (Web). Parenting plays an important role in the development of a child. Parenting is a boon. There are many parents who see parenting as a tiring or neglected job. Only when the parents sow good deeds in a child, can they reap good results. When the parents are not concerned about the child, the mind of the child remains empty and bad deeds are easily sowed in them. This makes the child involve in delinquent activities. Violence in the family environment is a crucial problem because it has huge impacts on the child. Violence may be loud or silent. Only the person traumatized can explain their violence. It is the duty of the parents to understand the changes in the psychological aspects of a child. When the negative signs that the children show are ignored, delinquency naturally falls in place. Children are pure and innocent; it is the surrounding that usually transforms a child in a positive or in a negative way.

Diana Blumerg Baumrind, a well renowned psychologist has conducted a research on parenting styles which is an appreciative area of research among the researcher's circle. According to Baumrind, parenting style can be divided into four (See Fig.1.)

Fig.1. Baumrind's Four Style of Parenting

AUTHORITARIAN PARENTING:

In this style of parenting, the children are expected to follow the strict rules established by the parents. When children fail to digress from the framed rules usually results in punishment. Authoritarian parents have a pride of doing this harsh treatment they fail to understand the psyche of the children which often results in violent crime.

AUTHORITATIVE PARENTING:

This parenting style is more democratic, because the parents establish rules and guidelines that their children are expected to follow. Authoritative parents are often responsive and listen to the queries of their children. When children fail to meet their expectation they are nurturing and forgiving rather punishing.

INDULGENT PARENTING:

Indulgent Parenting can otherwise be called as Permissive Parenting. They make very few demands on their children. Parents rarely discipline their children. Permissive parents are generally nurturing and communicative with their children. They often take status of a friend more than that of a parent.

NEGLECTFUL PARENTING:

Low demand, low responsiveness and little communication. The parents only fulfill the child's basic needs. They are detached from their child's personal life. These parents often ignore or reject the needs of the children.

In the anthology of *Teen Poems from behind Bars* written by youth at Denney Justice Centre in Everett Washington, in the poem "Poetic Justice" the teen boon quotes

My Momma told me to stay home
But boy, oh, boy did I want to roam
Hated the thought to be alone
So I hit the streets that I call home. (Lines 1-4)

In this poem, the juvenile delinquent reveals about his neglectful parents. They were able to provide basic needs, but the parents did not strongly impose their care and rules on the child. Even staying at home with his family, the child always felt lonely and alone so he chose street as his home and started committing crimes and later ended up in juvenile prison.

For a child to become a delinquent, family parenting acts as a foundation. In the poem "Choices" the delinquent child expresses her agony where she says:

I was just a little girl
I didn't know what was going on.
My Mom's boyfriend sneaked into my room
Every night...
She chose her boyfriend over her kid.
I felt sorry for the man who raped me (Lines 1-6)

When the parents fulfill their desires not listening to the likes and dislikes of a child, the child often undergoes traumatic experience. Behind any delinquency there is a violent behaviour of a parent or a stranger.

Juvenile Delinquency is a social problem that harms any segment of the population. It affects the government, community members and the economy. It puts strain on the government and economy because owners suffer huge losses and the government has to find facilities in order to promote the rehabilitation of the juveniles. *World Youth Report* states:

the problem of juvenile delinquency is becoming more complicated and universal and crime prevention programs are either unequipped to deal with the present realities or do not exist. Many developing countries have done little or nothing to deal with these problems, and international programs are obviously insufficient. Developed countries are engaged in activities aimed at juvenile crime prevention, but the overall effect of these programs is rather weak because the mechanisms in place are often inadequate to address the existing situation. (Web)

In 2006, Gleaner published an article titled "Addressing Juvenile Delinquency", it highlights the wounding of two teachers at St. Thomas Technical High and Knowlva Technical High in Hanover. The implication on teachers may involve emotional implication and professional implication. In the emotional implication, the teacher may be threatened by students because of their social background. Teachers may feel discouraged to teach still they have to be firm, brave, vigilant in handling students. In professional implication, teachers may feel frustrated and start conducting themselves in unprofessional ways like shouting at students, cursing and hitting. Teachers have to help their students to give proper guidance.

Implications on students may vary they may feel discouraged to attend class. Bullying students may be bullied by the delinquent students. It is necessary to conduct workshop and seminars with students, parents and guidance counsellors.

Childhood experiences are important in the development of criminality. Delinquency is not an intentional crime; juveniles often involve in anti-social activities when triggered by the environment in which they live. Blindly accusing them will not fetch good solutions. In order solve this problem, it is necessary to understand the situations and traumatic experiences that made a non-delinquent, a delinquent

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